

Neutrosophic Filters and Their Applications in BCK-Algebras

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Abstract: This paper explores the integration of neutrosophic logic into the algebraic structure known as *BCK* –algebra, with a particular focus on the development and analysis of neutrosophic filters. We present new definitions, fundamental theorems, and illustrative examples of important applications in decision-making. This study contributes to the theoretical foundations of logic under uncertainty and offers new directions for research into algebraic structures with incomplete information using neutrosophic filters in *BCK* –algebra.

Keywords: Neutrosophic sets theory; *BCK* –algebra; neutrosophic fine filter; neutrosophic *BCK* –algebra.

1. Introduction

BCK –algebra has attracted widespread interest in abstract algebra and mathematical logic since its introduction in the 1966 by Y. Imai and K. Iseki [1], due to its logical and structural properties that make it an effective tool for studying partial relations and binary operations. A prominent concept that emerged in this context is the "filter," which is used to analyze the internal structure of an algebra and identify the interconnected properties between its elements. Its forms have evolved to include primitive filters, suggestive filters, and intuition filters. Developed by Florentin Smarandache [2], neutrosophic logic represents a general framework that addresses the three values of truth (T), neutrality (I), and untruth (F), allowing for a more flexible representation of uncertain and imprecise knowledge compared to traditional fuzzy logic and others [3,4]. Recently, research has emerged to incorporate the concepts of neutrosophic logic into algebraic structures [5-7] and topological structures [8-16], most notably *BCK* –algebra. Several researchers have contributed to expanding the concept of filtering in *BCK* – algebra within this new context. In 2016 Martina Jency and Arockiarani [17] study single-valued neutrosophic ideals and discuss their different types, such as suggestive and intuitionistic. More recently, extended applications of so-called *MBJ* –neutrosophic ideals, which take into account multiple indicators and

weighted affinities, have emerged within extended BE –algebras and BCK –algebras. Research such as that by M. Mohseni Takallo, Rajab Ali Borzooei, Seok-Zun Song and Young Bae Jun. Abdelaziz Alsubie and Anas Al-Masarwah [18], [19] has provided new models for understanding the relationship between neutrosophic and ideals, and their role in characterizing eigenvalues and their associated algebraic properties. Saad H. Zail, Majid Mohammed Abed and Faisal AL-Sharqi [20], introduced neutrosophic ideals in neutrosophic BCK –algebra and Ω – BCK –algebra, B. Satyanarayana, Shake Baji and U. Bindu Madhavi [21] study BS-Neutrosophic Structures in BCK/BCI –Algebras. Furthermore, in the view of neutrosophic generalized semi generalized closed Sets, weak separation axioms, and generalized sg -closed sets with their continuity are deliberated by Imran et al. [22-24]. Abdulkadhim et al. [25,26] presented the ideas of generalized alpha generalized closed sets spaces and neutrosophic generalized alpha generalized separation axioms. In 2024 Bavanari Satyanarayana and Shake Baji [27], introduced A Study on the Polarity of Generalized Neutrosophic Ideals in BCK –Algebra. On the other hand, there has been a clear interest in applying single-valued neutrosophic filters, which can use precise numerical values to represent degrees of truth, neutrality, and rejection. Studies have shown that these filters are capable of integrating precise logical properties into algebraic models, contributing to improved modeling efficiency in artificial intelligence and decision-making systems. Given these developments, research into neutrosophic filters within BCK –algebra represents a promising path, especially in light of the trend toward developing cognitive systems capable of handling advanced ambiguity, inconsistency, and neutrality. Given the importance of this, we have presented in this work some important neutrosophic filters, their applications, some theories, examples and the relationship between them in BCK algebras.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1[1]: A BCK –algebra $(K, *, e)$ is a non-empty set with a binary operation $*$ and a constant e , satisfying the following axioms for all $k_1, k_2, k_3 \in K$:

$$Bck1. (k_1 * k_2) * (k_1 * k_3) = (k_3 * k_2)$$

$$Bck2. (k_1 * (k_1 * k_2)) = k_2$$

$$Bck3. k_1 * k_1 = e$$

$$Bck4. e * k_1 = e$$

$$Bck5. k_1 * k_2 = e \text{ and } k_2 * k_1 = e \text{ implies } k_1 = k_2$$

Definition 2.2[2]: A neutrosophic set as defined $N = \{ (k, T(k), I(k), F(k)): k \in K \}$, $T(k), I(k), F(k): K \rightarrow [0,1]$, $0 \leq T(k) + I(k) + F(k) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.3[23]: If $\pi: (K, *, e_1) \rightarrow (L, *, e_2)$ a BCK –homomorphism, then π satisfying: $\pi(k_1 * k_2) = \pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2)$, $\forall k_1, k_2 \in K$, and $\pi(e_1) = e_2$.

Definition 2.3: A neutrosophic BCK –algebra $(K, *, e)$ is a non-empty set with a binary operation $*$ and a constant e , satisfying the following axioms for all $k_1, k_2, k_3 \in K$:

1. $T((k_1 * k_2) * (k_1 * k_3)) \geq \{T(k_3 * k_2)\}$, $I((k_1 * k_2) * (k_1 * k_3)) \leq \{I(k_3 * k_2)\}$, $F((k_1 * k_2) * (k_1 * k_3)) \leq \{F(k_3 * k_2)\}$
2. $T((k_1 * (k_1 * k_2)) \geq \{T(k_2)\}$, $I((k_1 * (k_1 * k_2))) \leq \{I(k_2)\}$, $F((k_1 * (k_1 * k_2)) \leq \{F(k_2)\}$
3. $T(k_1 * k_1) = e$, $I(k_1 * k_1) = e$, $F(k_1 * k_1) = e$,
4. If $e * k_1 = e$, then $T(e * k_1) = T(e)$, $I(e * k_1) = I(e)$, $F(e * k_1) = F(e)$,
5. If $k_1 * k_2 = e$ and $k_2 * k_1 = e$, then: $T(k_1) = T(k_2)$, $I(k_1) = I(k_2)$, $F(k_1) = F(k_2)$.

3. Neutrosophic Filters in BCK –Algebra

This section introduces neutrosophic filters by definition of a fine filter in BCK –algebras and then extending it using the neutrosophic logic framework.

Definition 3.1: Let $(K, *, e)$ be a BCK –algebra. A non-empty subset $F \subseteq K$ is called a fine filter if it satisfies the following conditions:

1. $e \in F$
2. $\forall k_1, k_2 \in K, k_1 \in F$ and $k_1 * k_2 \in F, \Rightarrow k_2 \in F$

Definition 3.2: Let $(K, *, e)$ be a BCK –algebra, and let $N(K)$ be the neutrosophic extension of K , where each element $k \in K$ is associated with a neutrosophic triplet: $(T(k), I(k), F(k)) \in [0, 1]$,

representing the degrees of truth-membership (T), indeterminacy-membership (I), and falsity-membership (F) respectively.

Definition 3.3: A nonempty subset $N_F \subseteq N(K) = \{(k, T(k), I(k), F(k)), k \in K\}$ is called a neutrosophic fine filter of the BCK –algebra $(K, *, e)$ if the following conditions are satisfied:

1. $(T(e), I(e), F(e)) \in N_F$.
2. For any $k_1, k_2 \in K$, if $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$, and $k_1 * k_2 \in K$, then:

$$T(k_1 * k_2) \geq \min(T(k_1), T(k_2)), I(k_1 * k_2) \leq \max(I(k_1), I(k_2)), F(k_1 * k_2) \leq \max(F(k_1), F(k_2))$$

implies that $(T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in N_F$.

3. If $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$, and $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N(K)$, with: $T(k_1) \leq T(k_2)$, $I(k_1) \geq I(k_2)$, $F(k_1) \geq F(k_2)$. Then $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$.

Example 3.4: Let $K = \{e, k_1, k_2\}$, where the binary operation $*$ is defined by the following table:

Table (1): $(K, *, e)$ BCK-algebra

*	e	k₁	k₂
e	e	E	E
k₁	k ₁	E	E
k₂	k ₂	k ₂	E

1.It is easy to verify that this structure satisfies the axioms of a BCK-algebra.

2. Each element $k \in K$ is assigned a neutrosophic triplet $(T(k),I(k),F(k)) \in [0,1]$ as follows:

Table (2): values neutrosophic triplet $(T(k),I(k),F(k))$

k	T(k)	I(k)	F(k)
e	1	0	0
k₁	0.9	0.1	0.1
k₂	0.7	0.3	0.3

3. Define a neutrosophic fine filter $N_F \subseteq N(K)$ as:

$$N_F = \{(T(k), I(k), F(k)) \in N(K) \mid T(k) \geq 0.7, I(k) \leq 0.3, F(k) \leq 0.3\}$$

This includes the following elements: $(T(e), I(e), F(e)) = (1,0,0)$, $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) = (0.9,0.1,0.1)$

$(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) = (0.7,0.3,0.3)$. Hence, $N_F = \{e, k_1, k_2\}$ under neutrosophic conditions.

1. $(T(e), I(e), F(e)) = (1,0,0) \in N_F$

2.Let $a=k_1, b=k_2$. From the BCK operation table: $k_1 * k_2 = e$

$$T(k_1) = 0.9, T(k_2) = 0.7 \Rightarrow \min (T(k_1), T(k_2)) = 0.7,$$

$$I(k_1) = 0.1, I(k_2) = 0.3 \Rightarrow \max (I(k_1), I(k_2)) = 0.3, F(k_1) = 0.1, F(k_2) = 0.3 \Rightarrow \max (F(k_1), F(k_2)) = 0.3.$$

Now, check $T(e), I(e), F(e)$:

$$T(e) = 1 \geq 0.7, I(e) = 0 \leq 0.3, F(e) = 0 \leq 0.3 \Rightarrow (T(e), I(e), F(e)) \in N_F$$

3.Assume: $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) = (0.7,0.3,0.3) \in N_F$

Let $k_2 \in K$ such that: $T(k_2) = 0.8 \geq 0.7, I(k_2) = 0.1 \leq 0.3, F(k_2) = 0.1 \leq 0.3$

Then $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$ by condition 3.

The set N_F satisfies all three conditions of a neutrosophic fine filter .

Example 3.5:

Practical Example: neutrosophic fine filter for Teaching Methods Approval in a BCK –Algebra

Consider a Education decision-support system that evaluates methods teaching based on three key factors:

$T(x)$: Effectiveness or quality of the method, $I(x)$: Uncertainty or ambiguity in method, $F(x)$: not Effectiveness of method

We want to use a neutrosophic fine filter to select only those methods that:

Are sufficiently effective (high T), Have minimal uncertainty (low I), not effective (low F)

1. Let $K = \{e, M1, M2, M3\}$, where:

e : Active Learning and Problem-Based Learning (PBL), $M1$: Interactive lectures + Use of technology (e.g., educational videos, PowerPoint, digital quizzes), $M2$: Modified traditional method (e.g., direct instruction with some questioning/discussion), $M3$: Purely traditional method (rote memorization and lecturing without interaction or understanding). Define the operation $*$ as follows:

Table (3): $(K, *, e)$ BCK –algebra

$*$	e	$M1$	$M2$	$M3$
e	e	e	e	e
$M1$	$M1$	e	e	$M1$
$M2$	$M2$	$M2$	e	$M2$
$M3$	$M3$	$M3$	$M3$	e

This structure satisfies BCK –algebra.

the axioms of a

Assign neutrosophic Values:

Table (4): values neutrosophic triplet $(T(k), I(k), F(k))$

Methods	$T(x)$	$I(x)$	$F(x)$
e	1	0	0
$M1$	0.85	0.05	0.10
$M2$	0.65	0.20	0.20
$M3$	0.40	0.30	0.50

Let: $N_F = \{(T(x), I(x), F(x)) \in N(K) \mid T(x) \geq 0.6, I(x) \leq 0.2, F(x) \leq 0.2\}$

This filter includes: $M1 \in N_F, M2 \in N_F, M3 \notin N_F$ (due to low T and high F)

Verification of neutrosophic fine filter Conditions:

1. $(T(e), I(e), F(e)) = (1, 0, 0) \in N_F$.

2. Let $a = M1, b = M2$. From the *BCK* table: $M1 * M2 = e$.

Now, check: $T(e) = 1 \geq \min(0.85, 0.65) = 0.65, I(e) = 0 \leq \max(0.05, 0.20) = 0.20, F(e) = 0 \leq \max(0.10, 0.20) = 0.20 \Rightarrow (T(e), I(e), F(e)) \in N_F$.

3. If a Method $M \in N_F$, and another M' satisfies:

$T(M') \geq T(M), I(M') \leq I(M), F(M') \leq F(M)$, Then $M' \in N_F$ as well.

Hence: The set N_F satisfies all the required conditions of a neutrosophic fine filter in a *BCK* –algebra. Thus, it acts as a formal model for intelligent Method approval.

Proposition 3.6: Let N_F be a neutrosophic fine filter in a *BCK* –algebra $(K, *, e)$. For any $k_1, k_2 \in K$, if

$(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$, and $T(k_1 * k_2) \geq \min(T(k_1), T(k_2)), I(k_1 * k_2) \leq \max(I(k_1), I(k_2)), F(k_1 * k_2) \leq \max(F(k_1), F(k_2))$, Then $(T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in N_F$.

Proof:

From the Definition 3.3, the condition 2 guarantees that if the neutrosophic values of $k_1 * k_2$ satisfy the above inequalities, and $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$, then the resulting element $k_1 * k_2$ is also in the filter.

Hence, $(T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in N_F$.

Proposition 3.7: Let $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$, and suppose that for some $k_2 \in K, T(k_2) \geq T(k_1), I(k_2) \leq I(k_1), F(k_2) \leq F(k_1)$, Then $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$.

Proof:

According to the Condition 3 in the Definition 3.3, if an element $k_2 \in K$ has a higher degree of truth-membership and lower degrees of indeterminacy and falsity compared to some element $k_1 \in N_F$, then $k_2 \in N_F$.

Proposition 3.8: Let $\pi: (K, *, e_1) \rightarrow (L, *, e_2)$ be a homomorphism between neutrosophic *BCK* –algebras, and let $N_F \subseteq N(K)$ be a neutrosophic fine filter on K . The image

$\pi(N_F) = \{(\pi(k_1), T_K(k_1), I_K(k_1), F_K(k_1)) \mid (k_1, T_K(k_1), I_K(k_1), F_K(k_1)) \in N_F\} \subseteq N(L)$, is a neutrosophic fine filter in the neutrosophic *BCK* –algebra L .

Proof:

We will verify that $\pi(N_F)$ satisfies all three filter conditions in L :

1. Since $(e_1, T_K(e_1), I_K(e_1), F_K(e_1)) \in N_F$ and $\pi(e_1) = e_2$, and the neutrosophic values are preserved:

$(\pi(e_1), T_L(\pi(e_1)), I_L(\pi(e_1)), F_L(\pi(e_1))) = (e_2, T_K(e_1), I_K(e_1), F_K(e_1)) \in \pi(N_F)$, So the neutral element of L is in the image.

2. Assume: $(\pi(k_1), T_K(k_1), I_K(k_1), F_K(k_1)) \in \pi(N_F), (\pi(k_1 * k_2), T_K(k_1 * k_2), I_K(k_1 * k_2), F_K(k_1 * k_2)) \in \pi(N_F)$

Since π is a BCK –homomorphism: $\pi(k_1 * k_2) = \pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2)$

From the fact that both $k_1 \in N_F$ and $k_1 * k_2 \in N_F$, and since N_F is a filter in K , we conclude:

$$(k_2, T_K(k_2), I_K(k_2), F_K(k_2)) \in N_F \Rightarrow (\pi(k_2), T_L(\pi(k_2)), I_L(\pi(k_2)), F_L(\pi(k_2))) \in \pi(N_F).$$

3. Suppose $(k_1, T_K(k_1), I_K(k_1), F_K(k_1)) \in N_F$ and $k_1 * k_2 = e_1 \Rightarrow \pi(k_1 * k_2) = \pi(e_1) = e_2 \Rightarrow \pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2) = e_2 \Rightarrow \pi(k_1) \leq \pi(k_2)$. Since $\pi(k_1) \in \pi(N_F)$, it follows that: $\pi(k_2) \in \pi(N_F)$. Hence the image $\pi(N_F)$ is a neutrosophic fine filter in L .

Proposition 3.9: Let $\pi: (K, *, e_1) \rightarrow (L, *, e_2)$ be a homomorphism between BCK –algebras, and let $N_{F_1} \subseteq N(L)$ be a Neutrosophic Fine Filter on L . Define the preimage: $\pi^{-1}(N_{F_1}) = \{(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N(K) \mid (T(\pi(k_1)), I(\pi(k_1)), F(\pi(k_1))) \in N_{F_1}\}$. Then, $\pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$ is a neutrosophic fine filter on K .

Proof:

We will verify that $\pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$ is a Neutrosophic Fine filter on K .

1. Since $\pi(e_1) = e_2$ and $(T(e_2), I(e_2), F(e_2)) \in N_{F_1}$, it follows that: $(T(e_1), I(e_1), F(e_1)) \in \pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$.

2. Let $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)), (T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in \pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$ Then:

$$(T(\pi(k_1)), I(\pi(k_1)), F(\pi(k_1))), (T(\pi(k_2)), I(\pi(k_2)), F(\pi(k_2)))) \in N_{F_1}.$$

Since π is a homomorphism, we have: $\pi(k_1 * k_2) = \pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2)$.

Because N_{F_1} is a neutrosophic fine filter, then:

$$(T(\pi(k_1 * k_2)), I(\pi(k_1 * k_2)), F(\pi(k_1 * k_2))) = (T(\pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2)), I(\pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2)), F(\pi(k_1) * \pi(k_2)))) \in N_{F_1}.$$

So, $(T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in \pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$.

3. Assume, $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in \pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$, and: $T(k_2) \geq T(k_1), I(k_2) \leq I(k_1), F(k_2) \leq F(k_1)$.

Then: $(T(\pi(k_2)), I(\pi(k_2)), F(\pi(k_2))) \in N_{F_1}$, by the Condition 3 of N_{F_1} . Thus $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in \pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$.

Therefore, $\pi^{-1}(N_{F_1})$ is a neutrosophic fine filter.

Proposition 3.10: Let $\{N_F^i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of neutrosophic filters in $N(K)$,

such that their intersection is nonempty: $N_F = \bigcap_{i \in I} N_F^i \neq \emptyset$. Then N_F is also a Neutrosophic Fine filter.

Proof:

We will verify that three conditions of N_F

1. Each, N_F^i contains the neutral element $(T(e), I(e), F(e))$. Hence, $(T(e), I(e), F(e)) \in N_F$.

2. Let: $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)), (T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$. Then, for all $i \in I$:

$$(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)), (T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2))) \in N_F^i.$$

Since each N_F^i is a Neutrosophic Fine Filter, we have:

$$(T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in N_F^i \forall i \in I. \text{ Therefore, } (T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in N_F.$$

3. Suppose, $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$ and $T(k_2) \geq T(k_1), I(k_2) \leq I(k_1), F(k_2) \leq F(k_1)$. Then for all $i \in I$, by the Condition 3 of each N_F^i , we have $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F^i \Rightarrow (T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$. Hence, N_F is a Neutrosophic Fine Filter.

4. Another Neutrosophic Fine Filters:

This section contains two parts. We will provide a definition of some types of Neutrosophic Fine Filters.

4.1. Biggest and Unanalyzable Neutrosophic Fine Filter in BCK-Algebra

Definition 4.1.1: Let N_{F_1} be a neutrosophic fine filter on a BCK-algebra K , where, $N_{F_1}(k) = (T_{N_{F_1}}(k), I_{N_{F_1}}(k), F_{N_{F_1}}(k))$ for all $k \in K$. We say that N_{F_1} is a biggest neutrosophic fine filter if there does not exist another neutrosophic fine filter N_{F_2} on K such that: $N_{F_1} \subsetneq N_{F_2}$, that is: $T_{N_{F_1}}(k) \leq T_{N_{F_2}}(k), I_{N_{F_1}}(k) \geq I_{N_{F_2}}(k), F_{N_{F_1}}(k) \geq F_{N_{F_2}}(k)$ for all $k \in K$.

Definition 4.1.2: Let K be a BCK-algebra, and let $N: K \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a neutrosophic set such that

$N(k) = (T_N(k), I_N(k), F_N(k))$ for all $k \in K$. We say that N is a unanalyzable neutrosophic fine filter of K if: For any elements $k_1, k_2 \in K$, if $T_N(k_1 * k_2) \geq \min(T_N(k_1), T_N(k_2)), I_N(k_1 * k_2) \leq \max(I_N(k_1), I_N(k_2)),$

$F_N(k_1 * k_2) \leq \max(F_N(k_1), F_N(k_2))$, and if $(k_1 * k_2) \in N$, then $k_1 \in N$ or $k_2 \in N$.

Proposition 4.1.3: Every biggest neutrosophic fine filter are unanalyzable neutrosophic fine filter (i.e. If $N_F \subseteq N(K)$ is a biggest neutrosophic fine filter, then for any $k_1, k_2 \in K$, if $(T(k_1 * k_2), I(k_1 * k_2), F(k_1 * k_2)) \in N_F$, then $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1)) \in N_F$ or $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$).

Proof:

Assume that neither $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1))$ nor $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2))$ belongs to N_F . Then we can extend N_F by adding one of them, say $(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1))$, to form a strictly larger neutrosophic filter:

$N_{F_1} = N_F \cup \{(T(k_1), I(k_1), F(k_1))\}$. But this contradicts the biggest of N_F . Therefore,

$(T(x), I(x), F(x)) \in N_F$ or $(T(k_2), I(k_2), F(k_2)) \in N_F$. Thus, N_F is a unanalyzable neutrosophic fine filter.

4.2. Robust Neutrosophic Filter in BCK-Algebra

Let $T: K \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a neutrosophic membership function such that for each element $k \in K$,

$T(k) = (T_t(k), T_i(k), T_f(k))$ where: $T_t(k)$ is the degree of truth of k , $T_i(k)$ is the degree of indeterminacy of k , $T_f(k)$ is the degree of falsity of k . Define neutrosophic membership degree function $\aleph: K \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by:

$$\aleph(k)=\min\{T_t(k), 1-T_i(k), 1-T_f(k)\}$$

Definition 4.2.1: A fine filter F of a BCK-algebra K is called a robust neutrosophic fine filter if:

$$\text{For all } k_1, k_2 \in F, \text{ it holds that: } \aleph(k_1 * k_2) \geq \min\{\aleph(k_1), \aleph(k_2)\}$$

Example 4.2.2: In Example 3.2. Let us define a subset $F = \{e, k_1\}$.

We will verify whether it is: A Fine Filter, a robust neutrosophic fine filter under a certain membership function. A subset $F \subseteq K$,

It is easy to verify that $F = \{e, k_1\}$ satisfies the fine filter properties under these assumptions.

Now, we define neutrosophic membership values as:

Table (5): neutrosophic membership values

k	$T_t(k)$	$T_i(k)$	$T_f(k)$	$\aleph(k)=\min(T_t(k), 1-T_i(k), 1-T_f(k))$
e	1	0	0	$\min(1, 1, 1)=1$
k_1	0.8	0.1	0.2	$\min(0.8, 0.9, 0.8)=0.8$
k_2	0.4	0.3	0.5	$\min(0.4, 0.7, 0.5)=0.4$

We will
robust

Verify the

neutrosophic fine filter condition

We need to check whether for all $k_1, k_2 \in F = \{e, k_1\}$: $\aleph(a * b) \geq \min\{\aleph(a), \aleph(b)\}$

1. $a=e, b=e \rightarrow e * e = e$: $\aleph(e)=1, \min(\aleph(e), \aleph(e))=1 \Rightarrow \aleph(e * e)=1=1$
2. $a=e, b=k_1 \rightarrow e * k_1 = e$: $\aleph(e * k_1) = \aleph(e)=1, \min(1, 0.8)=0.8 \Rightarrow 1 > 0.8$
3. $a=k_1, b=k_1 \rightarrow k_1 * k_1 = e$: $\aleph(e)=1, \min(0.8, 0.8)=0.8 \Rightarrow 1 > 0.8$
4. $a=k_1, b=e \rightarrow k_1 * e = k_1$: $\aleph(k_1)=0.8, \min(0.8, 1)=0.8 \Rightarrow 0.8 = 0.8$

The function \aleph satisfies: $\aleph(a * b) \geq \min\{\aleph(a), \aleph(b)\}$ for all $a, b \in F$.

All conditions are satisfied. So, F is a robust neutrosophic fine filter in this BCK-algebra.

Proposition 4.2.3: Let $(K, *, e)$ be a BCK-algebra, and let $F \subseteq K$ be a fine filter. If, for all $k_1, k_2 \in F$, the neutrosophic membership function \aleph satisfies: $\aleph(k_1 * k_2) \geq \min\{\aleph(k_1), \aleph(k_2)\}$ then F is a robust neutrosophic fine filter in K.

Proof:

Let $k_1, k_2 \in F$. Since F is a fine filter, we know it is closed under implications and related operations in the BCK structure.

Now, by the condition: $\aleph(k_1 * k_2) \geq \min\{\aleph(k_1), \aleph(k_2)\}$

we ensure that applying the binary operation $*$ to elements of F does not decrease their minimum aggregated membership level.

Thus, for any $k_1, k_2 \in F$, the resulting element $k_1 * k_2 \in K$ still has a sufficiently high neutrosophic membership, and since $k_1, k_2 \in F$ (by closure), the neutrosophic structure is preserved.

Hence, F a robust neutrosophic fine filter.

Proposition 4.2.4: Let $(K, *, e)$ be a BCK-algebra, and let F_1 and F_2 be two neutrosophic fine filters on K .

Suppose that each filter has an associated neutrosophic membership function defined as:

$\aleph_{F_j}(k) = \min\{T_{F_j}^t(k), 1 - T_{F_j}^i(k), 1 - T_{F_j}^f(k)\}$, for all $k \in K$, $j=1,2$, where: $T_{F_j}^t(k)$ is the truth-membership degree of k in F_j , $T_{F_j}^i(k)$ is the indeterminacy- membership degree of k in F_j and $T_{F_j}^f(k)$ is the falsity-membership degree of k in F_j , $\aleph_{F_j}(k)$ is the neutrosophic membership degree function of k in F_j .

Assume the following two conditions hold:

1. $F_1 \subseteq F_2$,
2. $\aleph_{F_1}(k) \leq \aleph_{F_2}(k)$ for all $k \in F_1$.

Then: F_1 is called a Finer neutrosophic filter with respect to F_2 , F_2 is a coarser neutrosophic filter that contains F_1 .

Proof:

Let $k \in F_1$. Since $F_1 \subseteq F_2$, we also have $k \in F_2$. By assumption (2), we have:

$\aleph_{F_1}(k) = \min\{T_{F_1}^t(k), 1 - T_{F_1}^i(k), 1 - T_{F_1}^f(k)\} \leq \min\{T_{F_2}^t(k), 1 - T_{F_2}^i(k), 1 - T_{F_2}^f(k)\} = \aleph_{F_2}(k)$. This implies that every element $k \in F_1$, Therefore, F_1 is a Finer neutrosophic filter relative to F_2 , and F_2 is a coarser one.

Example 4.2.5: from Example 3.4, define two neutrosophic filters $F_1 \subseteq F_2$

Let $F_1 = \{e, k_1\}$, $F_2 = \{e, k_1, k_2\}$ So clearly: $F_1 \subseteq F_2$

Now, for each element $k \in K$, define:

For F_1 :

Table (6): neutrosophic membership values for F1.

K	$T_{F1}^t(x)$	$T_{F1}^i(x)$	$T_{F1}^f(x)$	$\aleph_{F1}(x)=\min\{T^t, 1-T^i, 1-T^f\}$
e	1	0	0	$\min\{1, 1, 1\}=1$
k_1	0.7	0.3	0.2	$\min\{0.7, 0.7, 0.8\}=0.7$

For F2:

Table (7): neutrosophic membership values for F2.

k	$T_{F2}^t(x)$	$T_{F2}^i(x)$	$T_{F2}^f(x)$	$\aleph_{F2}(x)=\min\{T^t, 1-T^i, 1-T^f\}$
e	1	0	0	$\min\{1, 1, 1\}=1$
k_1	0.9	0.1	0.1	$\min\{0.9, 0.9, 0.9\}=0.9$
k_2	0.6	0.3	0.2	$\min\{0.6, 0.7, 0.8\}=0.6$

Clearly $F1 \subseteq F2$. For all $k \in F1 : \aleph_{F1}(e)=1.0 \leq 1.0 = \aleph_{F2}(e)$, $\aleph_{F1}(k_1)=0.7 \leq 0.9 = \aleph_{F2}(k_1)$ So: $\aleph_{F1}(k) \leq \aleph_{F2}(k) \forall k \in F1$
 Both conditions of the Proposition 4.2.4 are satisfied, we conclude: F1 is a finer neutrosophic filter, F2 is a coarser neutrosophic filter, Because $F1 \subseteq F2$ and membership degrees are finer in F1 than in F2.

5. Conclusion

Neutrosophic filters play a crucial role in data analysis and interpretation, especially for data containing large amounts of data. Given this important role, in this paper, we present some neutrosophic filters in BCK-algebra, along with some theoretical and practical examples related to decision-making problems. In future work, we will present other types of filters in tectonic spaces, demonstrating the importance of these filters.

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